

Xylodiscula wareni Bogi & Bartolini, 2008 (Heterobranchia, Xylodisculidae): new records

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Abstract

Some shells of *Xylodiscula wareni* Bogi & Bartolini, 2008 are reported from Tuscan Archipelago, Gulf of Naples, Strait of Sicily and Spain. The present distribution of the species is discussed.

Riassunto

Xylodiscula wareni Bogi & Bartolini, 2008 è un microgasteropode dotato di conchiglia planispirale, sottile e trasparente, priva di evidente scultura e con una caratteristica carena periombelicale. L'animale è sconosciuto.

La specie è stata finora rinvenuta nelle acque siciliane e maltesi. Con la presente nota si segnala il ritrovamento di conchiglie in detriti provenienti da Livorno (Tirreno settentrionale), Punta Campanella (Tirreno centro-meridionale), Tarifa (Spagna meridionale) e si conferma la presenza della specie nel canale di Sicilia (Linosa). Ciò dimostra che la specie presenta un areale di distribuzione ben più ampio di quello precedentemente accertato, essendo diffusa almeno in tutto il Mediterraneo centro-occidentale. Anche la distribuzione batimetrica della specie è ampia, essendo stata rinvenuta dalla zona litorale fino a oltre 100 m di profondità.

Xylodiscula wareni Bogi & Bartolini, 2008 is a tiny gastropod with a small shell, fragile and transparent. It has a deep suture and an ovoidal, faintly triangular aperture. The umbilicus is wide with a patent keel, maybe the most noticeable shell feature. The animal is unknown (Bogi & Bartolini, 2008). It was described and recorded from few localities around Sicily (Bogi & Bartolini, 2008; Vazzana, 2010). No further records known. New findings for the Mediterranean Sea are reported in this note.

d: maximum diameter

nw: number of teleoconch whorls

sh: shell

1 sh from Punta Marroquí (Tarifa, Spain) by the local lighthouse, 07-07-2012, 39 m, in a shell grit sample col-

lected by SCUBA diving, in Raveggi Collection: d = 1.60 mm, nw = 2.2;

Fig. 1. *Xylodiscula wareni* Bogi & Bartolini, 2008. A-C, specimen from Punta Marroquí (Tarifa, Spain) (d = 1.30 mm), apical, basal and ventral views.

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5 shs from Punta Marroquí (Tarifa, Spain) east of the local lighthouse, 05-2011, 28 m, in a shell grit sample collected by SCUBA diving, 1 sh in Sbrana Collection: d = 0.90, nw = 1.5; 4 shs in Siragusa Collection: d = 1.30 mm (Fig. 1 A-C), 1.25 mm, 1.20 mm, 0.80 mm; nw = 2, 1.8, 1.7, 1.3 respectively;

1 sh off Capraia Island (Livorno, Italy), 03-2008, 103 m, in a sediment sample trawled by local fishermen, in Raveggi Collection: d = 0.90 mm, nw = 1.5;

1 sh from Linosa Island (Agrigento, Italy) 08-2011, 3 m, in a shell grit sample collected by diving, in Sbrana Collection: d = 0.90 mm, nw = 1.5;

Fig. 2. Distribution of *Xylodiscula wareni*, present study (black circles), past records (empty circles).

1 sh from Punta Campanella (Naples, Italy), 05-2009, 50 m, in a shell grit sample collected by SCUBA diving, in Bartolini Collection: d = 0.95 mm, nw = 1.7.

The taxonomic position of *Xylodiscula wareni* is uncertain, the attribution to *Xylodiscula* is only tentatively based on the general outline of the shell but some features (protoconch, keel) don't agree with the genus. It is a very poorly known species as only few empty shells have been found and nothing is known of its biology and ecology (Bogi & Bartolini, 2008). Our records widely extend its range to the north-central Tyrrhenian Sea and Southern Spain, and confirm the Channel of Sicily, so that a wider distribution, at least west-mediterranean, can be assumed. The bathymetry of the species is also slightly expanded, being recorded from littoral zone up to 100 m depth. Unfortunately no living specimens were found, so its relationships cannot be resolved. The scant records are likely due to oversight because of its small-sized, featureless shell as well as its typical habitat wasn't yet discovered. Further researches and the possible discovery of live specimens may give more accurate information on this rare species.

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